

Effects of *Melissa officinalis* L. Essential Oil in Comparison with Anaesthetics on Gill Tissue Damage, Liver Metabolism and Immune Parameters in Sea Bass (*Lateolabrax maculatus*) during Simulated Live Transport

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Abstract

In the current study, *Melissa officinalis* L. essential oil (MOEO), a novel sedative and anaesthetic, was employed in transport water to obtain a lower stress effect and higher survival rate for live marine fish. The effect of MOEO and various types of anaesthetics, administered at a low temperature on gill morphology, liver function and immunological parameters of living sea bass (*Lateolabrax maculatus*) subjected to transport stress, was evaluated to optimize the anaesthetic and sedative concentrations during live sea bass transport. Light microscopy and scanning electron microscopy of sea bass, subjected to simulated live transport for 72 h, demonstrated that the changes in the morphological characteristics of gill tissue treated with 40 mg/L MOEO (A3 group) were minimal in comparison to those observed in untreated sea bass. The results of pyruvate kinase (PK), phosphofructokinase (PFK), hexokinase (HK), hepatic glycogen (Gly), superoxide dismutase (SOD), lipid peroxides (MDA) and Caspase-3 assays indicated that the glycolysis rate, energy consumption, lipid peroxidation and hepatocyte apoptosis were the lowest in the A3 group. The values of the two immune parameters, lysozyme (LZM) and fish immunoglobulin M (IgM), indicated the strongest immunity ability in the A3 group. After 12 h recovery, sea bass treated with 30 mg/L MS-222 (B group) displayed a 100% survival rate, sea bass treated with 20 mg/L (A2 group) and 40 mg/L (A3 group) MOEO displayed a 96% survival rate, sea bass treated with 20 mg/L eugenol (C group) had a 94% survival rate, and untreated sea bass (CK group) had a 50% survival rate. Therefore, the addition of MOEO to the transport water had anaesthetic and sedative effects similar to MS-222 and eugenol. The results confirmed that the addition of MOEO to the transport water

could reduce tissue damage, energy metabolism, and the oxidative stress response in sea bass during transport.